

1. Introduction

The increase in the volume of information circulating in various systems of information collection, processing, and transmission leads to significant use of computing resources of hardware. Modern integrated decision-making architectures are based on: artificial intelligence and nanotechnologies and data compression technologies to increase the speed of their processing. At the same time, the use of information systems with elements of artificial intelligence will allow for increasing the efficiency of operations (combat actions) and will affect the doctrine, organization, and methods of application of groups of troops (forces).

Taking into account the above, an urgent scientific task is the development of an improved method of assessing the state of the object, which would allow for increasing the efficiency of the decisions made regarding the state of the object of assessment with a given reliability based on bio-inspired algorithms.

2. Methods

The evaluation of the state of the object of evaluation can be reduced to a typical task of a traveling salesman when converting the distance of a route to a metric. The presence of a metric in space allows you to make decisions about belonging to a set or about the similarity of sets based on a quantitative indicator. The size of the metric (distance) is often directly related to the probabilistic characteristics of assigning an element to a class [1–5]. The main goal of creating metrics is to increase efficiency in solving new practical tasks [6–10]. The step-by-step algorithm for solving the traveling salesman problem using the synthesized method, based on genetic and ant algorithms, can be presented in the following form [7]:

– *Step 1.* Initial data about the evaluation object are entered ($P_j(x_i, y_i)$), where: P_j – number of points; x_i, y_i – coordinates of points.

– *Step 2.* The degree of awareness about the state of the object of analysis and the degree of the noise of the data about the state of the object of evaluation is entered.

– *Step 3.* Individuals (cycles) are created, which means the route of passing all points and returning to the starting point.

– *Step 4.* The parameters of the ant cycle are set: the creation of a colony of N ants, entering the number of iterations of the ant algorithm.

METHODICAL APPROACH TO INCREASE THE SPEED OF DECISION-MAKING IN INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract: The relevance of the research lies in the need to increase the efficiency of the process of evaluating the object of evaluation while ensuring the given reliability, regardless of the hierarchical construction of the object of evaluation. The object of research is information systems. The subject of the study is the efficiency of the evaluation process. The hypothesis of the study is to increase the efficiency of the process at a given reliability. In the study, an improved methodology for increasing the efficiency of the evaluation process based on bio-inspired algorithms was proposed. In the course of the conducted research, the general provisions of the theory of artificial intelligence were used to solve the problem of analyzing the state of objects in intelligent decision support systems. The essence of improvement is to use the following procedures:

- taking into account the type of uncertainty about the state of the object of evaluation;
- taking into account the degree of the noise of the data on the state of the object of evaluation;
- using the ant algorithm and the genetic algorithm to find the path metric when evaluating the state of the evaluation object;
- deep learning of synthetic ants using evolving artificial neural networks.

An example of the use of the proposed methodology is presented in the example of the assessment of a hierarchical object. The specified model showed a 15–22 % increase in data processing efficiency due to the use of additional improved procedures.

Keywords: uncertainty, noisy data, the accuracy of assessment, reliability of decisions.

– *Step 5.* Initial passage of the colony by routes. The passage is carried out by choosing a branch for each ant. The probability of transition from a point i to j , k -th ant is calculated by the formula:

$$P_{ij,k} = \frac{\tau_{ij}^\alpha \eta_{ij}^\beta}{\sum_{m \in \mathcal{J}} \tau_{im}^\alpha \eta_{im}^\beta}, j = 1 \dots n, \quad (1)$$

where τ_{ij}^α – the number of pheromones on the branch from the point i in point j ; η_{ij}^β – proximity j -th points to the top i ; τ_{im}^α – the number of pheromones per branch from the point i in point m ; η_{im}^β – proximity j -th seats to the top m .

– *Step 6.* Calculation of the length of each route traveled by the ant using the formula for finding the distance between successive points of the route

$$r = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}.$$

– *Step 7.* The calculation of number of passes by ants along existing branches is calculated according to the following formula:

$$\Delta \tau_{ij,k} = \begin{cases} Q, & \text{if } (i, j) \in L_k, \\ r_k, & \\ 0, & \text{if } (i, j) \notin L_k, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where Q – a user-defined constant to increase or decrease the amount of pheromone on the field in question; r_k – the distance of the route traveled of ant k -th; L_k – route of k -th ant.

– *Step 8.* Pheromones update. The update will change on all existing branches and decrease in proportion to the factor ρ , the number of pheromones on the branches that the ants used to make their route will increase according to the formula:

$$\tau_{i\varphi(\tau+1)} = \rho \tau_{i\varphi(\tau)} + \sum_{\kappa=1}^v \Delta \tau_{i\varphi,\kappa(\tau)}, \quad (3)$$

where $\tau_{ij(t)}$ – number of pheromones to update; $\tau_{ij(t+1)}$ – number of pheromones after update.

– *Step 9.* After passing all iterations of the ant algorithm, the routes of the final iterations with the given levels of pheromones and transition probabilities are calculated.

– *Step 10.* Derivation of suboptimal individuals with minimum distance after completion of all iterations of the ant algorithm cycle.

– *Step 11.* The final selection of the most optimal individual from N is found and outputs the length of the route traveled by it.

– *Step 12.* Deep learning of ants synthesized during calculations in step 11. At this stage, the individuals that were obtained during step 11 are trained using the apparatus of artificial neural networks that evolve on the basis of the expressions proposed in the work [2].

– *Step 13.* Determination of the need to involve additional hardware resources of the system. At this stage, the need to attract additional system resources is determined on the basis of expressions (6)–(20) given in [9].

The end of the algorithm.

3. Results

The work of the assessment methodology based on bio-inspired algorithms was simulated in accordance with the algorithm and expressions (1)–(3). Simulation of the work of the proposed method was carried out in the Mathcad 14 software environment (USA). The assessment of elements of the operational situation of the group of troops (forces) was the task to be solved during the simulation.

The results of the comparative analysis using the proposed method, the method of branches and boundaries, the ant algorithm, and the genetic algorithm using annealing are shown in **Table 1**.

According to the results of the analysis of the data given in the **Table 1** shows that the proposed method has an acceptable computational complexity.

Table 1
Comparative analysis of bio-inspired algorithms

Number of intermediate solution points	Method of branches and boundaries	Genetic algorithm using annealing	Ants algorithm	The proposed method
N	T , sec	T , sec	T , sec	T , sec
5	0.282	0.264	0.276	0.284
10	0.723	0.414	0.4	0.414
15	6.641	0.96	0.999	1.099
20	10.7	2.433	2.5	2.512
30	21.3	4.4	4.5	4.643
40	42	8.2	7.9	7.232
50	56	10.515	10.1	9.142
100	120	20.2	17.6	19.52
200	727	82.8	74.2	80.8
Complexity	$O\left(\frac{(N-1)!}{4}\right) = O(N!)$	$O(5N^2 + 5) = O(N^2)$	$O(N^2 + N) = O(N^2)$	$O\left(\frac{5N^2}{2} + N\right) = O(N^2)$

In the range (from 50 to 100), the proposed method becomes more efficient in terms of algorithm operation time compared to other algorithms (faster than the branch-and-bound method by 82.58–83.54 % and the ant method by 7.62–9.71 %. The proposed method allows for obtaining ade-

quate solutions with a complex hierarchical structure of the monitoring object.

4. Discussion

The main advantages of the proposed evaluation method are:

- unambiguity of the received assessment of the state of the object;
- the universality of application due to adaptation of the system of indicators during work;
- high reliability of the obtained solutions when searching for a solution in several directions.

The disadvantages of the proposed method include:

- loss of credibility of the obtained solutions when searching for a solution in several directions at the same time;
- lower assessment accuracy compared to other assessment methods.

The proposed approach should be used to solve problems of evaluating complex and dynamic processes characterized by a high degree of complexity.

5. Conclusions

An algorithm for the implementation of the technique is defined, which allows:

- the type of uncertainty and noisy data is taken into account;
- take into account the available computing resources of the facility condition analysis system;

– carry out accurate training of synthesized individuals of the ant algorithm using the expressions developed in the work [2].

An example of the use of the proposed methodology was conducted on the example of assessing the state of the operational situation of a group of forces (forces). The specified model showed a 15–22 % increase in data processing efficiency due to the use of additional improved procedures.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Manuscript has associated data in a data repository.

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